

ASSESS THE ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIOUR OF ADJUSTMENT AMONG ADOLESCENT SCHOOL STUDENTS

UTUJE ALICE¹ & Dr. A. SUNDHARARAJAN²

¹*Medical and Psychiatric Social Worker, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India*

²*Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, SRM Nagar, Irungalur, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India*

***Corresponding Author: Utuje Alice, MSW, PGDC, Medical and Psychiatric Social Worker, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India. Pin Code – 620 017.**

Mail Id: kawuwalice@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

It is well known fact that every individual has the adjustment behavior but it is vary from person to person according to their age, sex, skill, ability, physical, intellectual, social and character development of the personality. This study is an effort to locate the adjustment problems of adolescents in the areas of social, emotional and educational adjustment. We have included 60 adolescent schools going children and conducted a questionnaire study among them. The adjustment inventory scores were noted as zero to one-point rating scale. Our results found that there is no significance between the study group and association between age and gender. The respondent number is very low this might be the reason for no significance. Further we need conduct a large population to prove the hypothesis.

KEYWORDS: *adolescence, adjustment, social and character development, personality*

INTRODUCTION

Adjustment is a process by which a living organism maintains a balance its needs and the circumstances that influences the satisfaction of these needs, the process of adjustment starts right from the birth of the child and continues till his death (Teyord (1963)). To analyze the process, we should study the development of an individual longitudinally from his birth onwards.

In other words adjustment is a state in the condition of harmony arrived at by person whom we call “well adjusted”. Also adjustment means achievement and which further means how efficiently an individual can perform this duties in different circumstances.

There are many criteria involved in good adjustment such as physiological comfort, physical health, work efficiency, social acceptance, etc., Criteria for adjustment differ from country to country and individual to individual depending upon social culture conditions, but in recent years psychologists have evolved certain criteria to assess the adequacy of adjustment of an individual in his environment.

All these stages are marked by different physical, intellectual, social and character development of the personality. There are certain periods in the process of development, where certain characteristic features of behavior stand out more prominently than other periods of life. Each stage of life has certain needs.

Adolescence is the most important and critical period of individual's development. It is the period of rapid revolutionary changes in the individual's physical, mental, moral, spiritual sex and social outlook. Human personality develops new dimensions. It is the period to learn new things. It is the period of anxieties, worries, conflicts and complexity. This period emerges from childhood and merges into adulthood.

Adolescence is the period of about eight to ten years when the individual is no longer a child but is not yet an adult. Station (341:170) states that the onset of adolescence occurs in the majority of boys and girls between the ages of eleven and fourteen and that the completion of adolescence takes place between the ages of eighteen and twenty one.

This study is an effort to locate the adjustment problems of adolescents in the areas of social, emotional and educational adjustment.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Tiruchirappalli district of Tamil Nadu during the month of January to march 2018. This is a prospective and observational type of study. We have included 60 adolescent those who gave their consent to participate this study. We got the consent from students, school administration and parents.

TOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION

Self- Prepared Questionnaire

We have formulated the socio demographic questions to collect personal details from the respondents with compromises of 12 questions and the adjustment inventory constructed and standardized by Dr. Srivatsava and Dr. Govinda Diwari, Agra Psychology Centre (Dr. Srivatsava and Dr. Govinda Diwari 1992) revised the scale. It is zero to one-point rating scale. Each item has two response alternatives. It has 80 items and all the items covered the various type of adjustment like home adjustment, educational adjustment, emotional adjustment and social adjustment. The questionnaire was approved by the institutional Ethics Committee

Scoring Procedure of Adjustment Inventory

The inventory is zero to one -point and the statement has each two choices. These are (i) yes (ii) no. Both positive and negative statements are included in the inventory. The negative items are 1,3,5,7,9,10,11,12,13,15,16,17,19,21,24,25,27,29,30,31,33,34,35,36,39,41,43,45,47,48,49,50,52,55,5

6,57,58,59,60,62,63,64,67,68,69,71,72,73,75,79 and 80. The score of the inventory is zero and one. The researcher undertook Quatail deviation analysis to categories of rows of scores as low, average and high. The inventory has 28 positive questions and 51 negative questions.

Reliability

Through the validity and reliability of the tool has been established already by its developers Dr. Srivatsva and Dr. Govinda Diwari it was again tested among the current population. The split method was adopted by the researcher based on verify the reliability. The obtained the reliability of the tool by the split method is 0.81 which shows it is highly reliable.

RESULTS

The questionnaire was distributed to all the participants and collected the filled up questionnaire back after. The data were tabulated and interpreted with the help of statistical tools like, Student t'test, Correlation '-test, Chi-test, bar diagram and Pie chart. The socio demographic results were shown in the figure 1 to 5. Association between family total income and their level of adjustment was shown in table 1. Differences between gender of the respondents and their level of adjustment and relationship between age of the respondent and their level of adjustments have shown in the table 2 and 3 respectively.

FIGURE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR AGE, GENDER & PERCENTAGE

FIGURE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR TYPE OF FAMILY & PARENT ALIVE

FIGURE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR PARENT'S EDUCATION

FIGURE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY THEIR DOMICILE

TABLE 1: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN FAMILY TOTAL MONTHLY INCOME AND THEIR LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENTS

SI	Monthly Income	Home Adjustment		Statistical Influence
		Low	High	
1	Below 20000	8 (72.7%)	3 (27.3%)	$X^2=1.153$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	20000-30000	3 (100%)	0 (0.0%)	
	Above 30000	33 (71.7%)	13 (28,3%)	
2	Emotional Adjustment			$X^2=3.930$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	10 90.9%	1 9.1%	
	20000-30000	2 66.7%	1 33.3%	
	Above 30000	29 95.7%	17 4.3%	
3	Social Adjustment			$X^2=0.305$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	6 54.5%	5 45,5%	
	20000-30000	2 66.7%	1 33.3%	
	Above 30000	29 63.0%	17 37.0%	
4	Educational adjustment			$X^2=2.924$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	5 45,5%	6 54.5%	
	20000-30000	3 100%	0 0.0%	
	Above 30000	24 52%	22 47.8%	
5	Overall Adjustments			$X^2=2.380$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	1 45.5%	6 54.5%	
	20000-30000	1 33.3%	2 66.7%	
	Above 30000	30 65.2%	16 34.8%	

TABLE 2: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENTS

S.No		Gender	Mean	Standard Deviation	Statistical Influence
1	Home Adjustment	Male (29)	17.793	1.8589	T = -0.542 Df = 58 P > 0.05 Not Significant
		Female (31)	18.000	1.000	
2	Emotional Adjustment	Male (29)	19.862	1.663	T=-0.927 Df=58 P>0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	20.451	3.0203	
3	Social Adjustment	Male (29)	16.2414	4.13003	T = 0.591 Df = 58 P>0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	16.8710	4.49799	
4	Educational Adjustment	Male (29)	18.3611	1.91465	T = 0.253 Df = 58 P>0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	18.2083	2.76593	
5	Overall	Male (29)	71.6552	6.09611	T = -1.521 Df = 58 P>0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	74.1290	6.47427	

TABLE 3: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGE OF THE RESPONDENT AND THEIR LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENTS

SI.No	Age & Various Dimension	Value	Statistical Influences
1	Age & Home Adjustment	-0.53	P > 0.05 Not Significant
2	Age & Emotional Adjustments	-.121	P > 0.05 Not Significant
3	Social Adjustment	-.043	P > 0.05 Not Significant
4	Educational Adjustment	-.047	P > 0.05 Not Significant
5	Overall	-.104	P > 0.05 Not Significant

TABLE 4: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN FAMILY TOTAL MONTHLY INCOME AND THEIR LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENTS

SI	Monthly Income	Home Adjustment		Statistical Influence
		Low	High	
1	Below 20000	8 (72.7%)	3 (27.3%)	$X^2=1.153$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	20000-30000	3 (100%)	0 (0.0%)	
	Above 30000	33 (71.7%)	13 (28,3%)	
2	Emotional Adjustment			$X^2=3.930$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	10 90.9%	1 9.1%	
	20000-30000	2 66.7%	1 33.3%	
	Above 30000	29 95.7%	17 4.3%	
3	Social Adjustment			$X^2=0.305$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	6 54.5%	5 45,5%	
	20000-30000	2 66.7%	1 33.3%	
	Above 30000	29 63.0%	17 37.0%	
4	Educational Adjustment			$X^2=2.924$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	5 45,5%	6 54.5%	
	20000-30000	3 100%	0 0.0%	
	Above 30000	24 52%	22 47.8%	
5	Overall Adjustments			$X^2=2.380$ Df=2 P>0.05 Not significant
	Below 20000	1 45.5%	6 54.5%	
	20000-30000	1 33.3%	2 66.7%	
	Above 30000	30 65.2%	16 34.8%	

TABLE 5: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENTS

S.No		Gender	Mean	Standard Deviation	Statistical Influence
1	Home Adjustment	Male (29)	17.793	1.8589	T = -0.542 Df = 58 P > 0.05 Not Significant
		Female (31)	18.000	1.000	
2	Emotional Adjustment	Male (29)	19.862	1.663	T = -0.927 Df = 58 P > 0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	20.451	3.0203	
3	Social Adjustment	Male (29)	16.2414	4.13003	T = 0.591 Df = 58 P > 0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	16.8710	4.49799	
4	Educational Adjustment	Male (29)	18.3611	1.91465	T = 0.253 Df = 58 P > 0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	18.2083	2.76593	
5	Overall	Male (29)	71.6552	6.09611	T = -1.521 Df = 58 P > 0.05 Not significant
		Female (31)	74.1290	6.47427	

TABLE 6: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGE OF THE RESPONDENT AND THEIR LEVEL OF ADJUSTMENTS

Sl.No	Age & Various Dimension	Value	Statistical Influences
1	Age & Home Adjustment	-0.53	P > 0.05 Not Significant
2	Age & Emotional Adjustments	-.121	P > 0.05 Not Significant
3	Social Adjustment	-.043	P > 0.05 Not Significant
4	Educational adjustment	-.047	P > 0.05 Not Significant
5	Overall	-.104	P > 0.05 Not Significant

DISCUSSION

The study of adjustment is very wide field of research by keeping in view the experience of thorough and systematic research. Students are facing educational adjustment problems. It means that they are not able to utilize their capabilities, capacities and potentialities in a proper way. Especially female students are facing more educational problems as compared to male students. Therefore, schools should organize competitive programmers for students so that they can explore their talent and capabilities in a proper way.

Education is a comprehensive and complex process aiming at bringing about not only change in knowledge and skill but also change in attitudes, behavior, values, needs and several other variables which are psychological and behavioral in nature.

The present study showed that there is no significance on the various adjustment patterns among adolescent school going students. The inclusion number is very less and this might be the reason for the level of significance.

CONCLUSIONS

To promote gender equity and equality, it is suggested that boys and girls should be treated equally at home as well as school by providing them equal opportunity in all the matters pertaining to their physical, educational and emotional development etc. Hence we concluded that the same study may be conducted in large scale including adults.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

We have collected from only one school and didn't see about the difference between boys and girls.

REFERENCES

1. Ahluwalia, S.P. and Kalia (1984). *Adjustment among High Achieving and Low Achieving Adolescents. Journal of Educational Research and Extension. Vol. 23 pp.147-152.*
2. Anderman, Eric, M. (2002). *California School Psychological. Vol. 7. pp. 5152.*
3. Angeline, H. Dollins&Mech (1956). *Trends in the Fears and Worries of School Children as related to Social-Economic Status on Anxiety. Journal of Educational Psychology. The American Psychological Association Inc. Washington.*
4. Asha, C.B. (1978). *An Empirical Study of the Adjustment Patterns of Creative Children in Secondary Schools. Ph.D. Psy. Kur. University.*
5. Bajpai, S. (1999). *Effect of Cast Belonging of Adjustment of Higher School Girls. Journal of Progress of Education. Vol. 73, No. 12 July 1999.*
6. Bhagia, N.M. (1966). *Study of the Problem of School Adjustment and Developing in Adjustment Inventory. Ph.D. Edu. (K.S.U.).*
7. Bhatt, L.J., Patel, P.M. Patel, M.M. and Parikh, D.S. (1961). *Inquiry into Psychological Factors related to Adolescent Adjustment. ICMR Project Faculty of Education Psychology, M.S.U. (ICMR-Finance).*

8. *Bhatt, K.K. (1971). Adjustment Problems of the under Achievers, University School of Psychology, Gujarat University.*
9. *Chopra, R. and Kalia, R. (2006). Adjustment Problems of Elementary School Children of Single Parental and Intact Parent Families. Indian Educational Abstracts Vol. 5. pp.36-40.*
10. *Gardia, Alok and Shandilya Shweta (2010). An Empirical Inquiry towards Relationship of Adjustment, Sense of Responsibility and Scientific Attitude among Adolescents. Gyan-The Journal of Education July-Dec. 2010. Vol. 7. No. 1 pp. 36-40.*
11. *Gyanani, T.C. and Gupta, Madhu (2001). Problems of First Generation Adolescent Learners. Journal of Indian Education, Feb. 2001. pp. 65-71 Hall, Stanley. Quoted in Essentials of Education Psychology by Aggarwal, J.C. (1994), New Delhi, Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd. pp. 164.*
12. *Jack, M. (1998). Child and Adolescent Social Work Journal. Vol. 15 (4), pp. 273-286. Jansen, Y.H.(1958). Influences of Personality Trait on Academic Success, Personal Guide, J., pp. 479-500.*
13. *Jersilld, A.T. (1978). The psychology of Adolescence, Mac Millan Company. As Quoted in Chauhan, S.S. Advanced Educational Psychology (6th Edition) pp. 74.*
14. *Joyce (1970). An Investigation of some Personality Characteristics of Achieving High School Students From Lower Socio-Economic Environments. Dissertation Abstract International Vol. 31 (4). p. 1623 A.*
15. *Kashyap, Veena (1989) Psychological Determinants of Adolescents Problems. Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University. Fourth Survey of Educational Research. Vol. I (1983-1988) NCERT New Delhi.*
16. *Kaul, Lokesh (2005). Methodology of Educational Research. Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi.*
17. *Kulhen, R.G. (1952). The Psychology of Adolescent Development, New York, Haper and Brothers.*
18. *Kumar, S.A. (1983). A Comparative Study Interests, Needs and Adjustment Problems of Gifted and Average Children, Ph.D. Education, New Delhi University. Fourth Survey of Educational Research Vol. I (1988). NCERT, New Delhi.*
19. *Kumari, Sushma (1990). Study of Personality Characteristics, Adjustment and Socio Economic status of Juvenile and Adult Offenders. Ph.D. Thesis, Punjab University. Fifth Survey of Educational Research, Vol. II (1988-1992) NCERT, New Delhi.*
20. *Lavin, D.E. (1965). The Prediction of Academic Performance. New York ,Russel Sage.*
21. *Leeper, R.W. (1948). Lewiv's Topological one Vecto Psychology. A Digest and Critique. Uni. Ore. Publ. Stud. Psychology Vol. 1.*
22. *Mattoo, B. (1972). Adjustment Differences at Different levels of General Intelligence and Socio-Economic status among Urban Adolescent Boys and Girls. Ph.D. Edu. Kur. University.*